

2022 YEAR IN REVIEW

Who we served

The Research Software Alliance (ReSA) acts as a hub, working through and with other communities, to bring together a diverse range of stakeholders – including funding agencies, research organisations, and research communities – who advocate for the recognition of research software and its integral role within the research ecosystem. Throughout 2022, ReSA engaged with key decision-makers and influencers in research software across the globe, as well as the broader research software community and those for whom software is just a small part of their interest.

Photo by Annelies Verhelst

ReSA Organisational Membership

In 2022, ReSA launched its Organisational Membership to enable organisations to demonstrate their commitment to international collaboration and innovation for research, by supporting the ReSA vision that research software and those who develop and maintain it are recognised and valued as fundamental and vital to research worldwide. Organisational Members have the opportunity to collaborate with decision makers and key influencers to create outcomes that will achieve both their goals and those of the international community. To become a ReSA Organisational Member, please provide your contact details and review the membership agreement, or contact memberships@researchsoft.org to discuss further.

Highlights

In the past year, we facilitated opportunities for the research software community to come together to:

- Co-develop the FAIR for Research Software Principles.
- Collaborate with other funders via the Research Software Funders Forum.
- Share diversity, equity, and inclusion best practices at Vive la différence - research software engineers.
- Network at Research Software Community Forums.
- Gather with global research software funders to set the agenda for supporting sustainable research software.
- Collaborate in task forces.

Photo by [Annelies Verhelst](#)

Task Forces

ReSA regularly convenes and facilitates task forces on specific issues impacting the global research software ecosystem. ReSA task forces enable the community to focus on and identify challenges and solutions for a particular area, at the international level. In 2023, the ReSA community will collaborate in these ongoing task forces:

- Research Software Landscape Analysis
- Code Availability Task Force
- Research Institution Policies to Support Research Software

Outputs

- Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software (Scientific Data article accessed over 8,000 times)
- Global gathering of research software funders sets the agenda for supporting sustainable research
- The Research Software Community Landscape in the Global South
- Report on Vive la différence - research software engineers
- Encouraging entry, retention, diversity, and inclusion in research software careers
- Overview of research software funding landscape

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Global South Mapping

ReSA continued to expand its 2020 mapping of the international research software community landscape, with assistance from contractors in Africa, Asia, and Latin America. A wide range of research software organisations and programs exist internationally to address the varied challenges in software productivity, quality, reproducibility, and sustainability. The resulting report, The Research Software Community Landscape in the Global South, identifies 126 organisations and communities and 62 funders as potentially supporting research software in the Global South.

Vive la différence - Research Software Engineers

ReSA convened Vive la différence - research software engineers, a hybrid event with an in-person element at the Lorentz Center in the Netherlands in April; and online events from March to April 2022 across different time zones. This workshop brought together 40 participants from across the globe, including representatives from international research software engineering communities and others interested in diversity, equity, and inclusion. A wide range of stakeholders who had not previously collaborated considered how research software engineering could be reframed to place diversity, equity, and inclusion as a central organising principle in research software.

Photo by [Sean Goggins](#)

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Forums

ReSA convenes the [Research Software Funders Forum](#) – a collaboration of more than 30 funding organisations committed to supporting research software, and those who develop it, as fundamental and vital to research. Since its inception in 2022, the Funders Forum has successfully engaged a broad range of participants from government, philanthropic, and industry organisations across the globe.

ReSA hosts occasional online [community forums](#) for the global research software community. In 2022, ReSA held five community forums with guest speakers who facilitated engaging discussion with participants.

The International Funders Workshop

In November, the Netherlands eScience Center and ReSA hosted the [International Funders Workshop: The Future of Research Software](#). During this workshop, a number of members from the [Research Software Funders Forum](#) came together with other organisations that support research software. Participants explored how to effectively fund new and existing research software. In total, more than 60 representatives from [45 organisations](#) attended the workshop. A major part of the workshop focused on drafting the [Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability](#). Drafting of the Declaration is continuing in 2023.

Photos by [Annelies Verhelst](#)

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Thank you!

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to our community, founding members, and organisational members – without whom none of this work would have been possible.

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ReSA is grateful its sponsors of the Vive la différence - research software engineers workshop: Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, and Ford Foundation; and the Dutch Research Council (NWO) and Leiden University for their support of the Lorentz Center.

ReSA is a fiscally sponsored project of [Code for Science & Society](#) and led by the [ReSA Steering Committee](#).